

Terpenoids : Part XXXIII. Synthesis of Isobisabolene

O. P. Vig, Inder Raj, J. P. Salota and K. L. Matta

Isobisabolene has been synthesised by an application of the Wittig reaction with methyltriphenyl phosphonium iodide on 4-(1-oxo-5-methyl-4-hexenyl)-cyclohexanone.

Isobisabolene, a sesquiterpene hydrocarbon isolated from the vetiver oil¹, was assigned the constitution (I) on the basis of physical and chemical evidences.

The present studies record a clean synthesis of this hydrocarbon (I). The chart given below illustrates the sequence of reactions employed.

Ethyl 7-methyl-3-oxo-6-octenoate (III) was prepared from 6-methyl-5-hepten-2-one with ethyl carbonate and sodium hydride under usual conditions². The compound (III) was condensed with ethyl β -bromopropionate in the presence of sodium ethoxide to give 4-ethoxycarbonyl-9-methyl-5-oxo-8-decenoate(IV) in 60 percent yield. The latter with ethyl β -bromopropionate and sodium ethoxide produced the triester (V) in 70 per cent yield. The triester(V) on hydrolysis and decarboxylation followed by esterification furnished the keto-ester(VI) in excellent yield.

The keto-ester (VI) was ketalised with ethylene glycol in the presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid³ when ethyl 4-2'-ethoxy-carbonylethyl-5,5-ethylenedioxy-9-methyl-8-decenoate in 75 per cent yield was obtained. Dieckmann condensation of the ketal diester (VII) afforded 2-ethoxycarbonyl-4-(1,1-ethylenedioxy-5-methyl-4-hexenyl) cyclohexanone (VIII) which was hydrolysed, deketalised and decarboxylated to give 4-(1-oxo-5-methyl-4-hexenyl)-cyclohexanone (IX) in 40 per cent yield.

1. P. S. Kalsi, K. K. Chakravarti and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 1165.
2. Mrs. G. Mukherji and J. C. Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2407.
3. E. J. Salmi, *Ber*, 1938, **71B**, 1803.

The diketone (IX) was subjected to the Wittig reaction⁴ with methyltriphenyl phosphonium iodide when 1-methylene-4-(1-methylene-5-methyl-4-hexenyl) cyclohexane(I), was obtained in 70 per cent yield.

The identity of the synthesised product (I) with natural isobisabolene was proved by the comparison of their I.R. spectra which were found identical (see experimental).

EXPERIMENTAL*

Ethyl 7-methyl-3-oxo-6-octenoate (III). 6-Methyl-5-hepten-2-one(II) (45 g.) in ether (60 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to a refluxing suspension of sodium hydride (13 g.) in ether (150 ml) and ethyl carbonate (75 g.) during 3 hr. The product was cooled, the excess of sodium hydride decomposed with absolute ethyl alcohol (5 ml) and the mixture

4. R. Greenwald, M. Chaykovsky and E. J. Corey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.

*Boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford, I.R. absorption spectra were recorded on Beckman I.R. 5 with sodium chloride optics, using a thin liquid film.

poured into excess of ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. Ethyl 7-methyl-3-oxo-6-octenoate (III) (35.3 g.) isolated in the usual way had b.p. 115–20°/mm., yield (50%), η_D^{20} 1.4500. (Found: C, 66.20; H, 9.40; $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.64; H, 9.15). It gave an intense violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Ethyl 4-ethoxycarbonyl-9-methyl-5-oxo-8-decenoate (IV). To a cooled solution of sodium (3 g.) in alcohol (50 ml) the above ketoester (25 g.) was added. The resulting sodio-derivative was mixed with sodium iodide (0.5 g.). After cooling ethyl β -bromopropionate (23 g.) was slowly introduced and the mixture heated for 5 hr. After working up in the usual way the keto-diester(IV) came over at 165–70°/5–7 mm, yield 22.5 g (60%), η_D^{20} 1.4740. (Found : C, 64.85; H, 9.20; $C_{16}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 64.40; H, 8.78%).

It gave a deep violet colour with alcoholic ferric-chloride. A higher boiling fraction (5 g.), b.p. 185–92°/5–7 mm., was also obtained (see below).

Ethyl 4-ethoxycarbonyl-4-2-ethoxycarbonylethyl-9-methyl 5-oxo-8-decenoate (V). A solution of sodium (2 g.) in alcohol (35 ml) was cooled. To it was added successively the ester (IV) (25 g.), sodium iodide (0.5 g.) and ethyl β -bromopropionate (15 g.) and the mixture was refluxed on steam bath for 10 hr. The keto-ester(V) was collected at 185–92°/5–7 mm., yield 23.1 g. (70%), η_D^{20} 1.4750. (Found : C, 63.51; H, 8.50; $C_{21}H_{34}O_7$ requires C, 63.29; H, 8.6%).

It gave no violet colour with ferric-chloride.

Ethyl 4-2-ethoxycarbonylethyl-9-methyl-5-oxo-8-decenoate (VI). The ketoester (V) (32.2 g.) and hydrochloric acid (200 ml.) were refluxed for 24 hr. The solution was evaporated and the residue (15.6 g.) was esterified with ethanol (50 ml.), sulphuric acid (1.5 ml.) and benzene (200 ml) to give the diethyl ester(VI) (16 g.) (80%), b.p. 174–80°/5–7 mm., η_D^{20} 1.4725. (Found : C, 66.42; H, 9.48; $C_{18}H_{30}O_5$ requires C, 66.23; H, 9.26%).

Ethyl 4-2'-ethoxycarbonylethyl-9-methyl-5,5-ethylenedioxy-8-decenoate (VII). A mixture of the keto ester (VI) (18 g.), ethylene glycol (4 g.), dry benzene (100 ml) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (50 mg) was refluxed in a flask fitted with a continuous water separator for 6 hr. till no more water separates. The reaction mixture was cooled and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. After removing the solvent the product was distilled, b.p. 186–92°/4–5 mm. Yield (15 g.) 75%, η_D^{20} 1.4765. (Found : C, 64.80; H, 9.40; $C_{20}H_{34}O_6$ requires C, 64.84; H, 9.25%).

4-(1-oxo-5-methyl-4-hexenyl)-cyclohexanone (IX). To sodium dust (3 g.) in benzene (100 ml) was added the diester (VII) (21 g.) under an atmosphere of nitrogen. The reaction started immediately and the mixture was refluxed for 10 hr. The contents were cooled in an ice bath and decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. The residue, after removal of the solvent gave a violet colour with alcoholic ferric-chloride.

The crude -keto-ester (10 g.) (VIII) which was not distilled for analysis was hydrolysed, decarboxylated, and deketalised by refluxing for 20 hr. with sulphuric acid (15%) (100 ml). The cooled solution was extracted with ether. After removal of the solvent the diketone

(IX) was distilled at 140°/5–7 mm. Yield 2.5 g (40%), η_D^{20} 1.4895. (Found : C, 74.8; H, 9.8; $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 74.96; H, 9.68%). I.R. spectrum shows peaks at 1720 cm^{-1} (strong, C = O).

I *Methylene-4-(1-methylene-5-methyl-4-hexenyl)-cyclohexane* (I). A solution of sodium methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen from sodium hydride (0.3 g.) and freshly distilled dimethyl sulphoxide (7 ml). The solution was cooled in ice-cold water and stirred during the addition of methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (5.2 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (14 ml), whereupon the reddish colour of methylenephosphorane was produced. After stirring at room temperature for 15 minutes, the diketone (IX) (0.6 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) was added and stirring continued for 3 hr. at 60°. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into cold water (50 ml.). The organic layer was taken up in petroleum ether and washed three times with cold water. After removal of the solvent the residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina (elution with petroleum ether 40–60°) and distilled under reduced pressure at b.p. 97–99°/7 mm. to give hydrocarbon (I) (0.39 g.) in 70 per cent yield. η_D^{22} 1.4966, lit.¹ η_D^{26} 1.4966. (Found : C, 88.21; H, 11.90; Calc. for $C_{15}H_{24}$, C, 88.23; H, 11.77%).

The synthetic hydrocarbon (I) was characterised through its I.R. absorption spectrum which showed peaks at 1640, 888 cm^{-1} $\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \end{matrix} \rangle C = CH_2$, 832, 815, 791 cm^{-1} (triplysubstituted double bond). For the natural isobisabolene the various characteristic peaks as reported by Bhattacharyya *et al.*, are 1640, 892 cm^{-1} $\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \end{matrix} \rangle C = CH_2$, 833, 813, 791 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

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Department of Chemistry,
Panjab University,
Chandigarh-14.

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